

INVESTIGATING THE FEASIBILITY AND SOCIETAL IMPACT OF MODULAR WASTE MANAGEMENT FACILITIES IN IKORODU, LAGOS STATE.

ADEBOLA-MOGAJI OLUWATOMISIN TIMOTHY

Department of Architecture, College of Environmental Sciences and Management, Caleb
University, Imota, Lagos State, Nigeria.
tt.moggz@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the feasibility and societal impact of modular waste management facilities in Ikorodu, Lagos State. It explores the effectiveness of implementing small-scale waste management facilities as a solution to the increasing waste challenges faced by communities. Through an extensive review of existing literature, on-site surveys, and data collection, the research aims to provide insights into the potential benefits and drawbacks of modular waste management facilities in addressing waste management issues in Ikorodu, particularly concerning community engagement. The findings from this investigation will enhance understanding of sustainable waste management practices and guide decisions aimed at improving waste management systems across communities.

KEYWORDS: Waste Management, Modular Structure, Small Scale facility, Societal Influence, Community Engagement, Ikorodu, Lagos State.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Waste management is a critical issue in both urban and rural areas, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Rapid population growth, urbanization, and industrialization have led to increased waste generation, posing significant environmental and public health challenges

(UNEP, 2020). In Ikorodu, Lagos State, inadequate waste management infrastructure exacerbates these challenges, resulting in pollution, health hazards, and environmental degradation (World Bank, 2018). Conventional waste management methods, such as landfilling, are no longer sustainable and require innovative solutions to address the growing waste problem. Even conventional waste management facilities face challenges like rising operational costs, environmental impact, logistics, and efficiency (Ajayi et al., 2019).

Modular waste management facilities offer a promising alternative by providing scalable, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly solutions to waste management issues (Kumar et al., 2021). This research aims to determine whether they are more feasible and effective solutions for managing waste, while also considering their broader impact on society, including economic, environmental, and social factors (Sarkodie et al., 2020). These findings will inform more sustainable waste management practices and policy decisions for our communities (Oladejo et al., 2021).

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature Review

Waste management presents a significant global challenge, particularly in urban areas, where factors such as population growth, industrialization, and urbanization contribute to a surge in waste generation (UNEP, 2020). In countries like Nigeria, inadequate waste management infrastructure exacerbates these issues, leading to environmental degradation, health risks, and resource depletion (World Bank, 2018). Conventional waste management methods like

landfilling and open dumping are no longer sustainable and require innovative solutions to address the escalating waste crisis (Ogunsote et al., 2019).

Modular waste management facilities have emerged as a promising alternative to traditional methods, offering scalability, flexibility, and efficient waste management processes (Kumar et al., 2021). These facilities, including material recovery centers, composting hubs, and decentralized systems, enable effective waste collection, sorting, recycling, and disposal (Sarkodie et al., 2020).

Existing literature emphasizes the potential benefits of modular waste management facilities in addressing urban waste management challenges (Finnveden et al., 2011). Studies have shown that these facilities can improve waste collection efficiency, increase recycling rates, reduce landfill waste, and mitigate environmental pollution (Arena et al., 2019).

Various case studies and pilot projects have demonstrated the effectiveness of modular waste management facilities in different contexts (Nair et al., 2020). For instance, material recovery centers and composting hubs in cities like Curitiba, Brazil, and San Francisco, USA, have successfully managed municipal solid waste and organic waste, resulting in significant reductions in waste sent to landfills, increased recycling rates, and environmental benefits (Wilson et al., 2018).

However, the implementation of modular waste management facilities faces challenges such as institutional support and community resistance (Srivastava et al., 2020). Additionally,

issues like technology integration, regulatory compliance, and stakeholder engagement require careful consideration for the success of such initiatives (Hoorweg et al., 2013).

Limited research has been conducted on the feasibility and effectiveness of modular waste management facilities in Nigeria, particularly in urban areas like Ikorodu, Lagos State (Oladejo et al., 2021). Nonetheless, insights from studies on waste management practices, policy frameworks, and community engagement offer valuable guidance for implementing modular waste management facilities in Nigeria (Ajayi et al., 2019).

Through a comprehensive literature review, this research aims to elucidate the potential benefits, challenges, and implications of modular waste management facilities for urban waste management in Nigeria. By analyzing successful case studies and identifying key factors contributing to their effectiveness, this study seeks to provide insights into the feasibility and societal impact of modular waste management facilities in Ikorodu, Lagos State, and beyond..

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research methodology employed in this study adopts a survey-based approach to gather comprehensive data on the viability and societal influence of modular waste management facilities in Ikorodu, Lagos State. Data collection methods include questionnaires, direct observations, interviews, and reviews of relevant documents. The questionnaire is meticulously structured to align with the study's objectives and research inquiries, specifically targeting professionals engaged in aesthetic design and architectural processes.

The selection of the sample is based on achieving a homogenous representation from various professional sectors, including software engineers, architects, construction engineers, and builders, employing Taro Yamane's formula for determination. Professionals are randomly chosen from diverse organizations and professional institutes' provided lists. To ensure the credibility of the research, data collection instruments include structured questionnaire guides for conducting interviews. Data analysis is conducted employing statistical methodologies such as frequencies and percentages, processed utilizing SPSS software. Confidentiality of data is strictly maintained,

respecting the level of consent provided by each interviewee.

4.0 RESULTS

The results of the investigation offer valuable insights into the practicality and societal consequences of modular waste management facilities in the Ikorodu area of Lagos State. These findings emphasize the potential advantages associated with the adoption of modular waste management facilities, including improvements in waste collection effectiveness, higher rates of recycling, and mitigation of environmental harm.

Furthermore, the research findings illuminate the barriers and challenges encountered in the implementation of modular waste management facilities. These obstacles include limitations in infrastructure, financial constraints, and opposition from local communities. Despite these hurdles, the research findings lay the groundwork for understanding sustainable waste management practices and informing policy decisions aimed at enhancing waste management systems in urban environments.

5.0 DISCUSSION

The aim of this research is to develop a compact waste management facility that effectively addresses the specific waste management needs of its community while remaining both economically viable and environmentally sustainable. This facility will integrate modern technologies and eco-friendly practices to ensure efficient waste handling, sorting, recycling, and disposal processes.

To realize this objective, the facility will be designed with modular features, allowing for flexibility and scalability to cater to the unique demands of the community it serves. Its strategic location within the community will optimize waste collection routes and minimize transportation expenses. Moreover, the facility will prioritize environmental sustainability by implementing measures such as waste segregation, composting, and harnessing energy from waste.

The design phase will involve extensive research and collaboration with waste management experts, environmental engineers, and community stakeholders to identify the most suitable technologies and strategies for the facility. Key considerations will include waste composition, volume, and characteristics to ensure optimal performance and resource utilization.

Furthermore, the facility's design will take into account the preferences and needs of the local community, incorporating aesthetic elements and public amenities to enhance its acceptance and engagement. Community participation will be encouraged through educational initiatives, outreach programs, and inclusive decision-making processes to foster a sense of ownership and responsibility for waste management practices.

Overall, the proposed waste management facility aims to serve as a model for sustainable waste management solutions, showcasing the practicality and effectiveness of small-scale approaches in addressing community waste management challenges. By implementing this facility, the goal is to promote environmental stewardship, enhance public health, and contribute to the overall welfare of the community.

6.0 CONCLUSION

In summary, this study has evaluated the practicality and social impact of modular waste management facilities in Ikorodu, Lagos State. The results indicate that these facilities present a hopeful remedy to the waste management issues encountered in urban settings. Nevertheless, their effective deployment necessitates overcoming infrastructure constraints, securing sufficient funding, and involving communities in waste management efforts. In essence, this research enhances comprehension of sustainable waste management methods and guides policymaking aimed at enhancing urban waste management systems.

7.0 REFERENCES

Asamoah, R. S., & Vlok, P. J. (2019). Sustainable waste management practices in developing countries: A review of municipal solid waste challenges in Accra, Ghana. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(6), 1074.

Cointreau, S. (2006). *Occupational and environmental health issues of solid waste management: Special emphasis on middle- and lower-income countries*. Washington, DC: World Bank.

De Silva, G. N., Ross, K. E., & Cordell, D. (2018). Phosphorus recovery and recycling from urban wastes in sub-Saharan Africa: Understanding impacts on food security and sanitation. *Science of the Total Environment*, 616-617, 1248-1260.

Hoornweg, D., & Bhada-Tata, P. (2012). *What a waste: A global review of solid waste management*. Urban development series; knowledge papers no. 15. Washington, DC: World Bank.

Kumar, S., & Nakayama, S. M. M. (2018). Environmental management for sustainable development in Nigeria: Challenges and policy options. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 206, 1121-1131.

Medina, M. (2015). Globalization, urbanization and municipal solid waste management in Africa. *Waste Management & Research*, 33(9), 858-862.

Narayan, K. A., Rajkumar, J. B., & Aremu, A. S. (2019). Solid waste management in Nigeria: Problems, prospects, and policies for sustainable development. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26(20), 20155-20167.

Ogwueleka, T. C. (2009). Municipal solid waste characteristics and management in Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Environmental Health Science & Engineering*, 6(3), 173-180.

Wilson, D. C., Rodic, L., & Scheinberg, A. (2012). Solid waste management: The regional approach. *Waste Management & Research*, 30(1_suppl), 22-28.

Zaman, A. U., & Lehmann, S. (2018). Factors influencing community participation in solid waste management: Case of Selangor State, Malaysia. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 20(2), 1352-1362.